

EARTH SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF RISK ASSESSMENT TECHNIQUES USING STUDIES ON NATURAL DISASTER VULNERABILITY AND COPING CAPACITY

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ABSTRACT

Effective risk management for natural disasters begins with risk assessment. It makes it possible to plan ahead, allocate resources, and prepare communities, all of which eventually lessen the toll that disasters take on both infrastructure and human lives. An essential idea in the realm of catastrophe risk reduction and management is vulnerability to natural hazards. It alludes to the possibility of loss and harm coming from exposure to natural hazards in a community, civilization, or system.

The ability of society to "stand against disaster" is reflected in its coping capacity, which is defined by the interplay of organizational, social, technical, and economic variables. The article's goal is to give comprehensive information about the many approaches for assessing coping capability and vulnerability that are applied to storm-related natural occurrences like flash floods.

The ultimate result can be presented in a variety of ways, including quantitative and qualitative ones, thanks to the methodologies' versatility. It depends on the tasks, challenges, and scientific puzzles that need to be solved as well as expert judgment. The resultant output has a high degree of practical application and sustainability.

Keywords: flash floods, natural disaster, vulnerability and coping capacity assessment.

INTRODUCTION

Risk of natural hazards is a phenomenon characterized by an uncertain outcome. The main purpose of the risk assessment is to identify and understand the potential impact of these hazards and develop strategies to mitigation and identification of specific actions that can reduce the potential impact.

Risk assessment includes the study of the following main factors: hazard, exposure, vulnerability and coping capacity.

The purpose of this study is to examine the vulnerability and coping capacity using two predefined research approaches and to perform a comparative analysis of the outcomes acquired. The chosen disaster phenomenon under examination is storms (flash floods), which exhibit a pronounced presence in the southern region of the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast, resulting in substantial destruction and economic losses.

Vulnerability and coping capacity assessments provide vital information for effective disaster risk management. By understanding these factors, authorities can make informed decisions, allocate resources efficiently, and empower communities to withstand and recover from natural disasters.

In the current context, it is imperative that there is a heightened emphasis on targeted collaboration at sectoral, bilateral, and regional scales. The implementation of robust data interchange and collaborative monitoring systems is of utmost importance. Enhancing collaboration among various businesses and nations, particularly in terms of synchronized financial support, research endeavors, and exchange of information, is of utmost importance in the endeavor to detect incipient indications of growing hazards, both domestically and internationally.

METHODOLOGY FOR RISK AND VULNERABILITY ASSESSMENT

The term risk refers to the probability of harmful consequences, or expected losses (deaths, injuries, property, livelihoods, economic activity disruption or environment damaged) resulting from interactions between natural or human-induced hazards and vulnerable conditions.

The term risk refers to the expected losses from a given hazard to a given element at risk, over a specified future time period. The first definition is given by [1]

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Hazard potential} \times \text{Vulnerability}$$

In following years, the aforementioned definition is further elaborated upon by:

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Hazard} \times \text{Vulnerability/Coping capacity} \quad [2,3]$$

$$\text{Risk} = \text{function of (Hazard, Exposure, Vulnerability)} \quad [4]$$

$$\text{Risk} = (w \cdot \text{Hazards} + w \cdot \text{Exposure} + w \cdot \text{Vulnerability}) - w \cdot \text{Coping Capacity} \quad [5,6]$$

The existing scientific research does not exhibit a preference for any particular aspect, although the investigation of vulnerability appears to be the prevailing focus. This phenomenon might be attributed to the fact that, depending on the selected risk assessment methodologies, variables pertaining to coping capability may also be regarded as indicators for vulnerability assessment.

Vulnerability and copy capacity assessments

Vulnerability assessments related to natural disasters are crucial for understanding and mitigating the impact of these events on communities, infrastructure, and the environment. Such assessments help in identifying weaknesses, evaluating potential risks, and developing strategies to enhance resilience. Comprehensive vulnerability assessment involves a multidisciplinary approach and collaboration among various stakeholders to effectively reduce the impact of natural disasters on communities.

Resent report pays special attention on the vulnerability and coping capacity assessment, using proposed chain on the Figure 1. A chain is an analytical tool that helps better understanding, systematization and factor' prioritization which drive vulnerability.

The present study includes a total of 47 indicators for coping capacity and vulnerability assessment. They

are based on the following main characteristics, which are crucial in risk management: Mitigating impact; Reducing vulnerability; Enhancing preparedness; Facilitating adaptation; Effective Resource allocation; Understanding a community's coping capacity helps in allocating resources effectively; Community engagement and empowerment; Economic stability.

Figure 1. Vulnerability impact chain [7,8]

Weighted arithmetic aggregation method for vulnerability and coping capacity assessment

The 'weighted arithmetic aggregation' method is used for vulnerability and coping capacity assessment. This is a common, simple and transparent aggregation procedure. Individual indicators are multiplied by their weights, summed and subsequently divided by the sum of their weights to calculate the composite indicator of a vulnerability component, as indicated in the following formula:^[8]

$$V_i = (i_1 * w_1 + i_2 * w_2 \dots + i_n * w_n) / \sum^1_n w \quad (1)$$

where V_i is the composite vulnerability indicator, i is an individual vulnerability indicator, and

$$C_i = (C_1 * w_1 + C_2 * w_2 \dots + C_n * w_n) / \sum^1_n w \quad (2)$$

where C_i is the composite copy capacity indicator, i is an individual vulnerability indicator.

Individual indicators are multiplied by their weights, summed and subsequently divided by the sum of their weights to calculate the composite indicator of a vulnerability

Weighting can have a major influence on your results and should be undertaken with care in a transparent process. So, the vulnerability indicators are specific, measurable, achievable, results-oriented and time-limited.

Adaptability

The concept of adaptability can be defined as the ability to consistently advance along one's existing trajectory^[9]. The implementation of this notion entails the development of inventions that have transformative effects on individuals' lifestyles. The phenomenon of

change has become an integral aspect of societal existence, persisting along a consistent trajectory. The core concept inherent in adaptability is transformative cognition and behavior, which pertains to the ability to alter trajectories or the aptitude to transition towards alternative trajectories in order to achieve long-term and sustainable progress.

The adaptive capacity can be considered either in the context of climate change and/or in the context of the considered natural disaster phenomenon. In the recent research sensitivity factors are approached in the same way as exposure. The leading question here is: what are the characteristics of the system under consideration that make it susceptible to adverse effects. Many factors identified under 'sensitivity' tend to be static and are inherent in the system. Other factors might be altered through human activity^[9].

Sensitivity factors included in the recent studies are related only to people exposure (residential building, total resident population during tourist season, local gross domestic product).

EARLIER INVESTIGATIONS

During 2003-2005 upper described methodology [1,2] was applied to the investigations in larger area of Southeast Bulgaria^[10]. Under research a complex risk analysis was performed covering natural and some man-made hazards. The emphasis was to the detailed study of vulnerability performing newly for that time method. The selected area covered the SE part of Bulgaria. It is an area with good developed tourism, economy, cultural and historical heritage. The population

density is different – high on the coast (especially during the high season) and much lower in the inland.

The climate of the selected area is strongly influenced by the Black sea and the Mediterranean. The climate along the Black Sea coast of southeastern Bulgaria is classified as a humid subtropical climate. The climate futures are changing towards north-south, as well as from the sea to the inland part of the region.

The rivers are relatively small (with low water-level during the summer and high flow in winter); relief is flat and low-mountain; the average population density is lower than 50 person for km²). In this area are located “Strandja” National park, nine natural, architectural end ethnographic reserves and over 12 protected territories.

Based on the initial and ongoing evaluations and studies, the vulnerability can be categorized into four primary groups: The social dimension of vulnerability;

Environmental aspects of vulnerability; Physical (constructional) vulnerability; Physical vulnerability Demographic vulnerability

NEW RESULTS

The new collected data and extended parameters assessment have been performed in the last Primorsko Municipality study – 2020-2023.

The natural occurrence of rapid onset disaster - storms (flash floods), is chosen for the comparison analysis for a pre-selected Bulgarian municipality (Primorsko municipality, Figure 2), for which a thorough risk assessment of hydro-meteorological and geological disasters was conducted [11,12]. For the risk assessment, an IDB-based technique was modified and implemented into practice [13]. One significant inclusion is to the incorporation of risk perception as a determinant in the evaluation of risks.

Figure 2. Location map of Primorsko Municipality (map sourced from Google Earth).

The method used to determine the indicator levels and weighting coefficients is the primary distinction between the two approaches. The indicator levels in the IDB's method for Hazard, Exposure, Vulnerability, Coping Capacity, and Risk Perception are established using a three-level scale ranging from 1 to 3 (low, medium, high). These five main factors are attached with a weighting coefficient, or

$$R = wH + wE + wV + wRP - wCC \quad [13]$$

$$0.32 * H + 0.35 * E + 0.34 * V + 0.34 * RP - 0.35 * CC \quad [13]$$

where w represents the weights and H , E , V , RP , and CC stand for Hazard, Exposure, Vulnerability, Coping Capacity, and Risk Perception [13]. The weighting coefficients' total sum must equal 100.

Thus, the sum of all the weighting coefficient attached to the relevant vulnerability indicators should be 34; the sum of all the weighting coefficient attached to the relevant coping capacity indicators should be 35, etc.

Naturally, the weighting coefficients and indicator levels in the DMZ technique have values between 0 and

1. The ultimate outcomes of both approaches are represented in the form of percentages ranging from 0 to 100 or as numerical values ranging from 0 to 1.

As a summary, we can describe the following: The IDB's method uses two types of weighting factors. The first are linked to the five risk factors: hazard, exposure, vulnerability, coping capacity, and risk perception. The sum of these indicators should be equal to 100, as indicated in the above formula. In the calculations presented in this way, the weight coefficients are very close in value since we assume that each of the risk assessment factors (hazard, exposure, vulnerability, coping capacity, and risk perception) has the same weight in the risk assessment. That is, in this case, priority is not given to one or another factor. Depending on the goals and objectives and mostly expert judgment, one factor may be prioritized over another. For example, coping resources have higher values than risk perception.

The second type of weighting coefficients is related to the individual indicators that are used to calcu-

late the five risk assessment factors. Each of the individual indicators is determined depending on the area for which the risk will be examined and the available data and information.

The DZM technique also incorporates weighting coefficients that are assigned to each indicator used in the vulnerability assessment. This approach employs a system of ten level of the weighting coefficients and ten indicator levels, ranging from 0 to 1. The DZM technique employs a broader spectrum of weighting elements and their associated metrics.

Considering the fundamental nature of the vulnerability and coping capacity notions, it is possible to utilize certain indicators that can serve as either vulnera-

bility indicators or resource indicators. The determination of the outcome is dependent upon the characteristics of the indicator and the evaluation conducted by experts. Therefore, various indicators can be identified, such as early warning systems, the presence of plans and strategies to mitigate specific natural phenomena, the availability of first responders, the ratio of doctors and hospital beds to the population, and so forth.

Twenty-eight indicators [11] are used to assess vulnerability, which are divided into the following groups – physical, demographic, social, economic, and environmental and climate change. The selected indicators are aligned with [14]. The results are presented on Figure 3.

Figure 3. Vulnerability and coping capacity levels for Primorsko municipality (Levels description; Very low 0-20; Low 20-40; Medium 40-60; High 60-80; Very high 80-100)

DISCUSSION

People are trying to understand things in new ways so they can deal with uncertainty, the unknown, and the way things change over time. If we want to be open to new things, we also need to be ready for the unexpected and learn how to deal with change [14].

As a result, risk analysis and assessment are now among the primary tools for risk management since they enable the scientific evaluation of possibly unfavorable future outcomes, as it shown on Figure 4.

Figure 4. Disaster risk assessment and management [4]

Since a gain in capacity also results in a decrease in vulnerability, vulnerability and capacity are inextricably linked and cannot be separated. Reducing vulnerability lowers the chance of calamity. Viability is concerned with the fundamental causes of a community's

vulnerability (structural issues, inherent vulnerabilities, etc.), whereas coping capability is concerned with preventive, mitigating, preparedness, response, rehabilitative, and reconstruction strategies. They represent all community-level programs, structures, and forms of

public and private investment that serve to avert catastrophes, lessen their consequences, equip society to handle extreme events, and aid in the recovery of victims. Coping ability thus indicates a community's potential for lowering risk, which can be actively addressed. In light of the aforementioned, we might characterize the connection between vulnerability and resources as a component of resilience to the particular process or event under consideration. Here, it's important to remember that coping capacity resources must be flexible to potentially harmful environmental phenomena.

Within this framework of thinking, it can be argued that the higher levels of coping capacity and lower level of vulnerability ensure a limited extent of harm and occurrence of human casualties. Consequently, it may be inferred that when vulnerability is significantly reduced and coping capacity substantially increased, the level of resilience would reach its peak.

The acquired data demonstrate a noteworthy variation in levels and values, respectively.

The analysis found that the lower values obtained for vulnerability are mainly due to the included, sensitivity, and coping capacity. In additional, ten levels of vulnerability indicators and their weighting coefficient allow for extremely precise numbers to be generated using the DMZ approach. Also, the coping capacity level are of higher value (71) due to adaptation strategies and resilience indicators included in the calculations.

It is important to stress that, for the designated coastal location, the chosen natural phenomena of storms is a complicated event in and of itself, posing a complex risk due to its association with excessive precipitation, river flooding, strong winds, and storm surge.

The IDB approach yielded low to medium resistance levels, whereas the DMZ method produced medium to high resistance levels. As previously mentioned, the primary cause of this discrepancy is the resilience indicators and adaptive techniques included in the coping capacity assessment. All of this points to the equal applicability of both approaches in practice, contingent upon data availability and, consequently, expert judgment. Further research is needed to determine how to apply the DMZ technique to the hazard, and exposure assessment in order to produce a thorough analysis of the two risk assessment methods.

It is also necessary to emphasize the following, bearing in mind Figure 5 and

Figure 6 [15]. The risks shown in the Mediterranean Sea region, including for the territory of Bulgaria, include health and well-being. Proceeding from these results, it is necessary that future assessments and risk analysis include or be oriented towards health and well-being, because, as it was emphasized above, risk is a human-being-oriented concept.

Key risks in the Mediterranean and their location for SSP5-RCP8.5 by 2100

Figure 5. Key risks in the Mediterranean and their location across the Mediterranean region for SSP5-RCP8.5 by 2100[15]

Key risks in the Mediterranean region

Figure 6. Summary of key risks for the Mediterranean [15]

Based on the conducted investigations and analyses, it has been decided that a crucial aspect and responsibility of risk assessment involves conducting assessments within specific and delineated geographical areas of limited size. This approach aims to achieve the highest level of precision and accuracy in obtaining reliable outcomes. The results that arise from varying degrees of risk, vulnerability, and coping resources in surrounding places, as well as for the same natural events, can exhibit significant differences. These disparities can be attributed to a multitude of variables that are associated with the unique traits and factors specific to each area.

Studies, models, and theories that have been created over the past few decades suggest that environmental risks will continue to have a greater impact and influence in many parts of the world. It is anticipated that new or more intense natural hazards would contribute to a rise in the disaster potential of natural occurrences in the future. Due to the rapid worldwide social and economic changes that are taking place, which impose "pressure" on both existing ecosystems and society, many locations are becoming more vulnerable at the same time.

The proposed research fully covers Joint Research Center [4] - European Commission' standards and guidelines. However, the current study does not purport to provide a comprehensive resolution to all issues pertaining to risk assessment across all domains. However, it does contribute to the field by proposing novel methodologies and concepts that can address scientific and practical challenges.

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